

Enhancing Fatigue Resistance and Low-temperature Performance of Asphalt Pavements Using Antioxidant Additives

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Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Recognizing
existence
of aging

1900 1910 1920 1930 1940 1950 1960 1970 1980 1990 2000 2010 2020

THE MODERN
ASPHALT
PAVEMENT

Clifford Richardson

By the action of the elements all asphalts undergo change. This change is due to oxidation, volatilization, and other molecular disruption, and the asphalt may pass through all the stages of brittleness to final crumbling or disintegration

Clifford Richardson, 1908

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Simulating
aging in lab

- By 1920s and 30s, the asphalt community had clearly recognised the existence of short- and long-term ageing
- By late 1930s, the impact of oxidation, both during short- and long-term ageing was well recognised in the asphalt community

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Studying
influencing
factors

1900 1910 1920 1930 1940 1950 1960 1970 1980 1990 2000 2010 2020

- Measuring differences in oxygen uptake by different types of asphaltic materials
- Demonstrating the differences in oxidation characteristics among asphalt binders from different sources
- Examining the role of mixture properties, the importance of asphalt film thickness and extraneous factors such as temperature sunlight
- Studying the influence of mixture parameters such as binder content, gradation, and air voids

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

- Developing kinetic models for oxygen absorption and reaction in asphalt binders
- Predicting oxidation that occurred in field while accounting for dictating factors such as asphalt binders, mixtures, pavement structures, and environmental conditions
- Using diffusion models at microscopic (binder and mastic) and macroscopic (mixture and pavement) length scales along with oxidation kinetics

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Investigating
reaction
pathways

1900 1910 1920 1930 1940 1950 1960 1970 1980 1990 2000 2010 2020

- Free radicals formed within the asphalt binder, then reacts with atmospheric oxygen to form peroxy radicals
- The peroxy radicals then decompose to form ketones or react with other asphalt molecules to form hydroperoxide
- Free radicals that continue the reaction

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

- Peroxide decomposers and carboxy acid amine salt were as antioxidants in **1960s**, but this success could not be replicated with binders from other sources at lower concentrations
- More materials, including ZDC were used as antioxidants and were found to be effective in **1970s** in Australia and New Zealand
- Antioxidants were used for field trials in **1980s and 1990s**
- Antioxidants were also used as co-polymer for bitumen since **2000s**
- Global consortium of antioxidation research of bitumen was established in **2022**

Background on Ageing

So why have we not focused on anti-oxidants?

- Complexity
- Diversity
- Reaction pathways have been relatively less understood

Two approaches:

1. Mechanistic approach
 - understand the mechanism
 - find agents that interrupt or prevent oxidation
2. Empirical approach (“brute force”)
 - identify best candidates based on current knowledge
 - cast a wide net to examine efficacy

Current members of consortium

United States

United Kingdom

China

Netherlands

Germany

Austria

France

Belgium

India

Colombia

Lithuania

Brazil

Historical account of asphalt ageing and innovations

Consortium Goal: Phase 1/2

Inverted Round-Robin Model- Phase 1

Phase 1 – Part 1

- 2 to 3 regional binders
- 4 reagents as anti-oxidants (maybe 2 different Percentages)
- 20 to 30 possible binders for testing

Phase 1 – Part 2

- 2 to 3 regional binders
- 2 reagents as anti-oxidants
- 6 to 12 possible binders for testing
- **Full group participation**

Experimental Methods : Part 1

Lignin

Calcium Hydroxide

Zinc Diethyldithiocarbamate

Phenothiazine

Experimental Methods: DSR, FTIR, Poker Chip etc...

Key Results from Phase 1

Key Insights and Takeaways

- Physicochemical processes governing antioxidant behaviours in binders are exceedingly complex

- Rheological behavior is crucial
- The reduction of oxidation serving as a precursor driving mechanism

- ZDC is a highly effective additive, exhibiting strong effectiveness with most binders

- Considerable anomalies were observed in the results
- Interaction is intricate and multifaceted

Testing Programme

Purity	Density (g/cm ³)	Formula	CAS No.	Chemical structure	Picture
98%	1.48	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₄ Zn	14324-55-1		

Binder testing

- Linear amplitude sweep (LAS)
- Low-temperature frequency sweep

Mixture testing

- 4PB at 25°C
- IDT at 25 °C
- IDT at 10 °C

Fatigue performance of binders

- Fatigue life of ZDC-modified bitumen was greater than that of neat (unmodified) bitumen at the strain level of 5%
- Bitumen was more susceptible to strain after ageing, antioxidant reduced the strain-susceptibility of bitumen

Low-temperature performance of binders

- ZDC improved the thermal cracking resistance of bitumen at low-temperatures, especially when the ageing situation was severer
- ZDC reduced the cracking susceptibility of bitumen at low-temperature

Fatigue performance of mixture — 4PB tests

- Ageing reduced the fatigue life of asphalt mixtures, but ZDC can slow down this reduction

Fatigue performance of mixture — IDEAL-CT tests

- **ZDC** can improve the cracking resistance of mixtures at **intermediate** temperature

Low-temperature performance of mixture — IDEAL-CT tests

- **ZDC can improve the cracking resistance of mixtures at Low temperature**

Effectiveness index (EI)

Effectiveness index (EI)

$$EI = ADI_{unmodified} - ADI_{modified}$$

- Antioxidant could effectively and systematically **slow down** the performance deterioration of bitumen and mixtures
- The effectiveness was **not directly correlated** with the dosage of antioxidant
- The performance of **mixtures** in relation to performance properties improved from **9% to 69%**, while **bitumen** showed an improvement from **1% to 28%**
- The improvement in **low-temperature** properties ranged from **13% to 69%**, whereas the improvement in **fatigue** performance ranged from **1% to 44%**

Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS)

- 15 T FTICR mass spectrometer at University of Warwick (UK)
- Ultrahigh resolution analysis, unrivalled performance for complex mixtures
- With appropriate data analysis methods, can be used to assign tens of thousands of molecular formulae

Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS)

- Distribution of molecular classes (e.g. N-, S-, O-containing species).
- Changes in composition with oxidation/ageing or with additives (lignin, bio-binders, antioxidants).
- Insight into polarity, aromaticity and potential structure–property relationships.

APPI-FTICR MS spectrum of bitumen

Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS)

Zoom in x4,000

Showing only m/z 534.10-534.55

~30 assignments per Da

x1000
for a whole
spectrum

x9
for all
samples

Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS)

Notes on data analysis

- **“Heteroatom class” or “Compound class”**
 - Examples: “HC” (hydrocarbon, no heteroatoms), S1, N1, etc.
 - For mass spectra: [H] label added for even electron ions (e.g. protonated/deprotonated species); otherwise odd electron (radical) ions
- **Carbon number**
 - Useful for overall size of molecule; indication of alkyl chain lengths
- **Double bond equivalents (DBE)**
 - For DBE, use $C_cH_hN_nO_oS_s$ where:
 $DBE = 1 + c - h/2 + n/2$
 - Rings and double bonds within the carbon frame
 - Integer values for neutrals or odd electron ions, half-integer values for even electron ions

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